

Table continued.

Scientific name	Family	Water depth (cm) at which species is most common ^a	Importance ^b	Flowering during study ^c
<i>Ludwigia hyssopifolia</i> (G. Don) Exell	Onagraceae	1	3	+
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl.	Pontederiaceae	3	3	+
<i>Rotala indica</i> (Willd.) Koehne	Lythraceae	2	3	-
D. Littoral				
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R. Br. ex Roem. & Schult.	Amaranthaceae	1	1	+
<i>Hedyotis racemosa</i> Lam.	Rubiaceae	1	2	+
<i>Hygrophila phlomisoides</i> Nees	Acanthaceae	0	2	-
<i>Limnocharis flava</i> (L.) Buch.	Butomaceae	3	1	+
<i>Lindernia pusilla</i> (Willd.) Bold.	Scrophulariaceae	0	3	+
Miscellaneous weeds				
A. Floating				
<i>Azolla pinnata</i> R. Br.	Azollaceae	3	1	?
<i>Lemna minor</i> L.	Lemnaceae	3	1	?
<i>Pistia stratiotes</i> L.	Araceae	3	1	?
<i>Salvinia cucullata</i> Roxb. ex Bory	Salviniaceae	3	1	?
<i>Wolffia arrhiza</i> (L.) Wimm.	Lemnaceae	3	1	?
B. Submerged				
<i>Chara zeylanica</i> Kl. ex Willd.	Characeae	3	1	?
<i>Nitella</i> sp.	Characeae	3	1	?
<i>Nitellopsis</i> sp.	Characeae	3	1	?
<i>Oscillatoria</i> spp.	Oscillatoriaceae	3	1	?
<i>Spirogyra</i> spp.	Zygnemataceae	3	1	?
<i>Urticularia aurea</i> Lour.	Lentiburiaceae	3	1	+
C. Emerged, rooted				
<i>Marsilea minuta</i> L.	Marsileaceae	2	3	?
<i>Urticularia bifida</i> L.	Lentiburiaceae	1	1	+
<i>Xyris indica</i> L.	Xyridaceae	1	3	+

^a3 = deep (>10 cm), 2 = medium (5-10 cm), 1 = shallow (0-5 cm), and 0 = dry. ^b3 = primary weed species, 2 = secondary weed species, 1 = incidental weed species. ^c+ = flowering observed, - = flowering not observed, ? = not detected on a macroscopic scale.

Weeds in rice in Madagascar

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We surveyed several rice areas of Madagascar to determine the most important weed species associated with rice. Field visits and farmer interviews were conducted in the Middle West (Kianjasoa, Mahasolo, and Tsiroanomandidy) in Nov 1990, and in the Central Highland (Manjakandriana, Sambaina, Ambanitsena, and Miarina) and the North West (Tsararano, Mampikony, and Port Berge) in May 1992.

Approximately 50 ricefields in the

Middle West, 30 in the North West, and 20 in the Central Highland were examined and major weeds were identified and collected for a herbarium. Where possible, we visited fields in the company of farmers. Otherwise, weeds were collected and brought to farmers for them to identify with their local names and to rank according to importance. Final ranking was determined by the number of times each species was mentioned as most important, second most important, and so on. Unidentified weeds that farmers considered important were taken to the Departement Flore du Parc Botanique et Zoologique de Tsambazaza in Antananarivo for identification.

In the Middle West, all farmers ranked *Striga asiatica* as the most troublesome

weed because it is difficult to control and causes serious crop damage even before emergence (see table). Farmers estimated that it caused 60-100% yield loss. *Rottboellia cochinchinensis* was considered the second most important weed species because of its abundance and high seed production.

Sedges, particularly *Cyperus difformis*, *Cyperus iria*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, and *Eleocharis* spp., were considered the most problematic weed species in Tsararano, Marovoay, because of their abundance. Farmers also considered *Cynodon dactylon* to be a problem, but only on bunds.

Farmers in Mampikony ranked *Aeschynomene indica* as the worst weed because of its abundance and vigorous growth. The weed residues left in the

Major weed species in several rice areas as ranked in importance by farmers. Madagascar, Nov 1990 and May 1992.

Weed species	Local name
Middle West ^a (Upland rice ecosystem)	
<i>Striga asiatica</i>	Arema
<i>Rottboellia cochinchinensis</i>	Tsaganday
<i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i>	Bakakely
<i>Urena lobata</i>	Kerijy
<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	Angamay Mahapady
<i>Digitaria setigera</i>	Marorantsana Fandroahy
North West (Rainfed lowland rice ecosystem)	
Tsararano, Marovoay	
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	Somotrosy
<i>Cyperus iria</i>	Chipisoka
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	Sombengy
<i>Ludwigia adscendens</i>	Volondrano
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	Menavavy
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Fandotrarana
Mampikony	
<i>Aeschynomene indica</i>	Renaud
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i>	Ranjamena
<i>Brachiaria distachya</i>	Tergal
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i>	Tsikababanga Tainbiriky
Port Berge	
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i>	Bomata
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	Sombengy
<i>Aeschynomene indica</i>	Renaud
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	Menavavy
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	Somotrosy
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	Tsimitamita
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	Tsivakimpanoto Ampody Tsifaryfary Tsikababanga Tainbiriky
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i>	Tsikababanga Tainbiriky
Central Highland ^b (Rainfed lowland rice ecosystem)	
<i>Potamogeton fluitans</i>	Valatendro
<i>Scirpus juncooides</i>	Ahidratsy
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	Tsiriry
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> ^c	Tsivakimpanoto Ampody Tsifaryfary Karangimena
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> ^d	Karangimena

field after rice harvest were a problem during land preparation.

In Port Berge, *Sphenoclea zeylanica* was the major weed problem. Farmers considered it the most difficult to control because of its abundant growth.

Farmers in three villages of the Central Highland considered *Potamogeton fluitans* to be their worst weed. Control of *P. fluitans* requires

large amounts of hand weeding. Few farmers thought that the weed could be controlled by plowing and harrowing after rice harvest and subsequent drying during the dry season.

It was observed that farmers considered a weed important based on abundance in the field and difficulty of control. ■

Weed - fish interactions at different water levels in irrigated ricefields in Northeast Thailand

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We conducted a field trial on eight farms in the Lam Dom Noi irrigated area in Ubon Province, Northeast Thailand, in the 1987 dry season. Each farmer provided two rice - fish fields and two control fields that were 0.1-0.5 ha. Rice crops were transplanted within a 14-d period. Management was left to the farmers.

Fish were stocked at densities of 60-200/ha. A mixture of *Cyprinus carpio* L. (common carp), *Tilapia nilotica* L. (*× mossambica*) (Nile tilapia), and *Puntius gonionotus* Bleeker (Thai silver barb) was used. The fish weighed 10-100 g.

The water depth was read at 2-d intervals from transplanting until weed density measurements at 40 d after transplanting (DT). We studied 6- or 12-m² sample plots, depending on field size, in each field. Plot area was reduced to 0.25 m² where plots had more than 1,000 plants/m². Weed plots were grouped according to average water depth. Weeds/plot were averaged for each weed group,

Number of weeds (+ SE) in different weed groups at 6 water depths. Ubon Province, Northeast Thailand, 1987 dry season.

Item	Weeds (no.) + SE											
	3 cm		5 cm		7 cm		9 cm		11 cm		13 cm	
Sedges												
Rice-fish	138	+ 44.2	106	+ 28.1	81	+59.6	60	+19.6	20	+ 6.5	15	+12.5
Control	184	+ 47.9	146	+ 36.8	63	+19.5	28	+ 8.6	7	+3.0	3	+ 2.2
Broad-leaved weeds (excluding <i>M. vaginalis</i> and <i>M. crenata</i>)												
Rice-fish	176	+ 49.6	60	+ 20.9	25	+11.0	170	+29.2	65	+42.3	3	+ 2.3
Control	170	+ 94.6	124	+ 23.5	100	+32.6	79	+40.9	9	+4.2	5	+ 2.1
Grasses												
Rice-fish	3.9	+ 1.92	2.7	+ 0.68	2.5	+ 0.87	1.4	+ 0.60	0.6	+0.60	0.0	+ 0.0
Control	2.1	+ 0.79	1.2	+ 0.46	0.6	+ 0.38	0.8	+ 0.22	0.2	+0.20	1.8	+ 0.47
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>												
Rice-fish	10.5	+ 4.37	14.6	+ 4.12	11.9	+ 6.19	16.3	+ 4.88	18.1	+6.50	14.6	+12.3
Control	9.8	+ 5.65	7.4	+ 1.74	10.8	+ 3.10	12.9	+ 3.86	3.8	+1.28	2.0	+ 1.41
<i>Marsilea crenata</i>												
Rice-fish	0.0	+ 0.00	0.0	+ 0.00	3.4	+ 1.93	20.7	+ 7.09	6.2	+5.55	11.4	+ 7.28
Control	29.6	+ 14.3	11.8	+ 5.87	5.7	+ 2.76	11.5	+ 3.85	11.8	+7.71	0.0	+ 0.00
Area (%) covered by non-algae weeds												
Rice-fish	7.0	+ 1.60	3.3	+ 0.68	3.4	+ 0.67	5.9	+ 1.41	3.3	+1.19	2.4	+ 1.27
Control	5.0	+ 2.64	4.3	+ 2.45	3.1	+ 0.92	2.2	+ 0.88	0.4	+0.24	0.0	+ 0.00
Plots (no.)												
Rice-fish	13		26		10		21		10		8	
Control	11		20		19		20		5		4	

^aVillages of Kianjasoa, Mahasolo, and Tsiranomandidy.
^bVillages of Manjakandriana, Sambaina, Ambanitsena, and Miarina. ^cRanked fourth in Miarina, Central Highland.
^dRanked fourth in Sambaina, Central Highland, and fifth in Miarina, Central Highland.